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D2.3 Reports on 4 INFRAFRONTIER Annual Conferences

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INTRODUCTION

The primary outreach strategy and tool for the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project were the annual INFRAFRONTIER stakeholder conferences. The scientific focus of these conferences was on translational research and technology developments. The stakeholder conferences also supported engagement with the INFRAFRONTIER user community and collaboration partners from academia and industry. These events were later rebranded as 'INFRAFRONTIER Conferences' for easy recognition and to welcome non-stakeholder attendees outside the INFRAFRONTIER consortium. The conference webpages can be found [here](#).

An engaging and inclusive conference format was designed for each event with a focus on the European mouse research communities as well as interactions with other international networks and a specific translation research area. The conference was generally a 2-days event aiming for around 200 attendees. Key objectives of the INFRAFRONTIER stakeholder conferences were to:

- 1) promote resources and services among existing users and potential new user groups,
- 2) demonstrate the utility of mouse models via translational and preclinical research highlights and
- 3) actively engage with INFRAFRONTIER user communities covering individual researchers, research consortia and industry.

Overall, the stakeholder conferences facilitated alignment of INFRAFRONTIER services with the needs of its broad scientific community paving the way for new research, development and innovative projects. The scientific program broadly covered presentations from INFRAFRONTIER users, contributions from global consortia like the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) and use of IMPC mice and phenotype data in translational research and disease model identification. A further focus is on innovative technologies like CRISPR-Cas9 driving high-throughput pipelines, deep phenotyping and on new research instrumentation. This was also complemented by ethical issues and relevant regulations and research policies. The conference program also included panel discussions, poster sessions and exhibition and partnering opportunities for industry representatives when strategically and logistically feasible.

Thanks to INFRAFRONTIER2020, the INFRAFRONTIER consortium has established the 'INFRAFRONTIER Conferences' as major engagement events for the international mouse research community as well as the personal medicine, rare diseases, ageing, functional genetic variances and cancer initiatives. It is planned to extend these events beyond the project period and the next steps will be to devise a sustainability strategy and financing plan encompassing organisational experiences, attendee feedback and actual meeting costs.

INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2017: Advancing Personalised Medicine with Animal Models

Details

Dates: 14 – 16.11.2017

Venue: Royal Olympic Hotel, Athens, Greece

Registrations: 196

Website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-research-infrastructure/public-relations/infrafrontier-impc-stakeholder-meeting-2017>

About the Conference

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting: “Advancing Personalised Medicine with Animal Models” which was jointly organized with the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) with participants from INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC members as well as from external institutes like University of Limoges, Tel-Aviv University, Yonsei University and North-West University. The meeting was also attended by participants from the pharmaceutical and biomedical industry like Genentech, Sonidel Ltd, Metabolon, Biomedcode, AYOXXA Biosystems and Sable Systems Europe.

The main focus of the meeting was to facilitate active discussions on the advancements in CRISPR/Cas9 technology and its implementation in INFRAFRONTIER with a wide range of international INFRAFRONTIER stakeholders like the IMPC, personalised medicine initiatives, rare disease networks, funders and the INFRAFRONTIER user community. Adoption and implementation of state-of-the-art technologies is an integral aspect of sustainability and this conference funded by the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project aimed to accomplish this.

The meeting was divided into three sessions with the first session dealing with the main topic of advanced personalised medicine using animal models while the second session provided

an update on the activities of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) in the form of the IMPC annual meeting. The last session highlighted the importance of responsible research and its contribution to animal welfare and experimental reproducibility.

CRISPR/Cas9 technology has revolutionized the field of genetic engineering and ushered in a new era of genome editing. It has expedited the process of generating transgenic mice and also made it more precise and reliable. Thus, there's an urgent need to discuss the implications of this novel technology on the generation of mouse models for human diseases and their application in personalised medicine. Having recognized this challenge, INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC aimed to meet the following objectives with this stakeholder meeting:

- Raise awareness of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms among current personalised medicine initiatives, funders and policy makers.
- Share advances in CRISPR/Cas9 technology to model human disease conditions.
- Present use cases for the utility of animal models for identifying targets for precision therapies.
- Strengthen interactions with personalised medicine initiatives and rare disease consortia.
- Discuss the ethical aspects of genome-editing and data quality and reproducibility in preclinical research.

Agenda

The conference agenda can be found [here](#).

Conference Overview

The stakeholder meeting started with an opening lecture by Prof. Dr. Martin Hrabě de Angelis introducing the objectives of the meeting, the organizers and the main participant groups. He also highlighted the importance of animal models in precision medicine and stated that animal-based studies will be indispensable for the development of personalised medicine. This was followed by a keynote lecture by Prof. Dr. George Kollias (BSRC Fleming) on the contribution of disease modeling to precision medicine initiatives. He presented the example of modeling rheumatoid arthritis using the human TNF transgenic mouse and introduced the human-to-mouse comparison pipeline at the gene, pathway and network level.

The rest of session 1 was divided into four chaired sub-sessions. The first of these discussed the use of genome editing approaches like CRISPR/Cas9 for modeling human disease conditions and included modeling human disease variants and in-depth analysis of CRISPR off-targets. The following sub-sessions detailed the contribution of large-scale mouse resources and EU research infrastructures to the field of personalised medicine as well as the accompanying policy, regulatory and funder perspectives. The first day of the meeting ended with the panel discussion on aligning the development of large-scale mouse resources with precision medicine initiatives.

The IMPC annual meeting constituted the second session of the stakeholder meeting and began with opening remarks from Prof. Dr. Steve Brown on the role of IMPC in delivering genetic mouse models for precision medicine. The rest of the session provided an update and overview of several IMPC activities namely mouse production (e.g. technological advances, mouse line QC), phenotyping and data analysis (immunophenotyping, metabolomics), data and programme integration (data integration opportunities, partnerships) and outreach and dissemination (website redesign, publications). In addition, the session also incorporated brief summaries and discussions on IMPC activities. A feedback session from the IMPC steering committee and poster session ended the second day of the meeting.

The third session focused on the importance of responsible research in view of personalised medicine and its implications on experimental reproducibility, animal welfare and ethics. Prof. Dr. Luis Montoliu started the session with his talk on fostering responsible research with genome editing technologies like CRISPR/Cas9. Other talks focused on the ethical considerations of editing the mammalian genome and the biobank requirements in the post-CRISPR/Cas9 era. In lieu with the topic, the second keynote lecture by Prof. Dr. Malcolm Macleod delved into data quality and reproducibility aspects of preclinical research. The session and meeting ended with high quality scientific talks from young research investigators in the form of stakeholder presentations encompassing a wide-range of studies highlighting the use of mouse disease models in advancing personalised medicine.

Conference Outlook

Most discussions echoed the thought that mouse models are indispensable for the advancement of personalised medicine as they confirm causation, help understand the underlying pathophysiology and can act as reliable surrogates for treatment studies.

The following considerations needed to be kept in mind to use mouse models in personalised medicine:

- Patient genetic variations should be accurately modelled into the mouse genome for validating the pathogenesis of the genetic variant.
- The mouse phenotypic measures should match the patient disease i.e. similar pathophysiology should be established in the relevant mouse model.
- The disease phenotype should be tested on multiple mouse model backgrounds to expose the degree of variability or robustness of the mouse model and help identify modifier loci leading to the discovery of important ancillary pathways implicated in the diseased state.

It was also unanimously acknowledged that genome-editing is a key technology driving further the advancement of Personalised Medicine with animal models. In this regard, CRISPR/Cas9 will expand available precision model organism resources and promote technology development for rapid assessment of human disease variants leading to the generation of reliable and robust animal models. Moreover, CRISPR opens the following promising scientific avenues for Precision Medicine:

- Creation of complete allelic series of a genetic disease.
- Experimental validation of the phenotypic output of combinatorial gene variations.

- Humanization - the progressive reshaping of the whole mouse genome to reflect human genetic variation.
- Comprehensive understanding of genetic background and its effect on Mendelian disease mutation

There was also overall support on harnessing mouse diversity resources and CRISPR to functionalize the human genome which consists of decoding human genetic variation with mouse diversity pipelines and the treatment of complex diseases in these pipelines.

INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2018: Advancing Rare Disease Research and Gene Therapy Applications with Animal Models

Details

Dates: 03 – 04.12.2018

Venue: Hilton Park Hotel, Munich, Germany

Registrations: 191

Website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-research-infrastructure/public-relations/infrafrontier-impc-stakeholder-meeting-2018>

About the conference

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting: 'Advancing Rare Disease Research and Gene Therapy Applications with Animal Models' (3rd – 4th December 2018) was attended by participants from 22 countries across Europe, East-Asia, North America and Australia, and was jointly organized with the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) in Munich, Germany.

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project funded the Stakeholder Meeting that aligned the INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms with current rare disease research and personalised medicine initiatives, and enabled interactions with human genetics centres, clinical consortia and biobanks. It also underscored the significant impact of mouse genetics on understanding human genetic variation and disease. Several rare disease networks also presented their operation and connected with model organism communities. International experts in the field of gene therapy presented their latest cutting-edge research in context to applied animal models and gene editing therapeutic interventions for rare diseases. This conference contributed to INFRAFRONTIER sustainability by promoting access to its resources to

international rare diseases and gene therapy researchers, contributing to its global effort to maintaining and expanding collaborative networks.

The Stakeholder Meeting was broadly divided into the following topics:

- Advancing Rare Disease research with animal models
- Gene therapy applications using animal models
- Rare disease initiatives
- Young investigator / Stakeholder presentations

The main objectives of the meeting were:

- To raise awareness of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms among the rare disease community.
- To present collaborative mechanisms advancing rare disease research with model organisms.
- To present use cases for the utility of model organisms to advance rare disease research.
- To present advances in the preclinical testing of gene therapy approaches to cure human diseases.
- To strengthen interactions with rare disease and clinical research consortia.

Agenda

The conference agenda can be found [here](#).

Conference Overview

Prof. Dr. Martin Hrabě de Angelis started the stakeholder meeting by announcing the objectives of the meeting, the organizers and the main participant groups. He also highlighted the importance of animal models in uncovering the genetic causes of rare disease and in advancing the development of novel effective gene therapies. This segued in to the first session entitled 'Model organisms facilitate rare disease diagnosis and therapeutic research' with the Keynote lecture by Dr. Shinya Yamamoto, who presented his cutting-edge research from the Model Organisms Screening Centre (MOSC) on functional genetic studies carried out using *Drosophila* and Zebrafish. These genetic studies were focused on studying the gene variants identified in patients enrolled in the UDN using whole exome and whole genome sequencing. The first session ended with talks about the IMPC and Monarch Initiative. Dr. Terry Meehan, who took over for Dr. Melissa Haendel, introduced the Monarch Initiative - a large-scale bioinformatics resource connecting genotypes and phenotypes from many species with the goal to aid genetic disease research and presented on the use of phenotypic similarity to animal models to aid disease diagnosis.

Prof. Dr. Olaf Riess from Solve-RD started session 2 that focused on EU and national rare disease initiatives. "Solve-RD - solving the unsolved rare diseases" is an EC-funded research project set out to develop multiomics diagnostic tests in patients for whom whole exome sequencing was not successful. His presentation was followed by Dr. Daria Julkowska (INSERM, France) who presented the rare disease landscape in Europe which includes, among

others the International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDiRC), E-Rare and European Reference Networks. Dr. Julkowska also gave a comprehensive overview of the new European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD), an EU-wide and patient-centred Cofund initiative that fosters creation of the RD research ecosystem to support innovative translational research for the benefit of patients. The second session ended with presentations from Genomics England and the Canadian Rare Diseases Models and Mechanisms (RDMM) network.

Panel Discussion: Advancing rare diseases diagnosis and their therapeutic research with model organisms – Building bridges between basic and clinical research

Chair: Prof. Dr. Paul Lasko – McGill University

Panellists:

Dr. Shinya Yamamoto – Baylor College of Medicine / UDN

Prof. Dr. Steve Brown – MRC Harwell / IMPC

Prof. Dr. Olaf Riess – Universit of Tübingen / Solve-RD

Dr. Philippe Campeau – University of Montreal / RDMM

Discussion topic	Input from the panelists
Primary challenges in aligning clinical and biomedical research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical and geographical barriers between clinical and basic researchers. • Lack of effective communication between clinical and biomedical researchers. • Lack of easily accessible federated databases with diagnostic data. • Alarming increase in the number of variants of unknown significance (VUS) in genetic diagnosis.
Opportunities in aligning clinical and biomedical research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify clinically relevant genes as priorities for functional studies. • Develop larger reference databases of variants and linking them to phenotypes. • Develop and adopt standards for phenotype description and data sharing. • Promote cross-disciplinary understanding and opportunities for interaction. • CRISPR-based opportunities for VUS interpretation and generating precision mouse models.
Resources needed to overcome the challenges and pursue opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced phenotyping involving deep sequencing to understand all underlying genetic changes for a subset of complex genetic disorders. • Improved data integration enabling closer cooperation between model organism resources, like the Alliance of Genome Researchers, and clinical geneticists. • Involve experts specialized in specific areas. For example, IMPC's mouse phenotyping pipeline would be a valuable

	<p>resource. IMPC also plans to develop specific capacities to incorporate specific pathogenic variants into its standardized phenotyping pipelines.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revised data protection policies for patient data that do not hamper data integration or data sharing. • Unique patient IDs to prevent self-matching of patients in different studies.
<p>Next steps to facilitate better alignment of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC resources and expertise with global rare disease research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A follow-up expert group meeting for data integration between model organism resources and rare disease clinical data. This will also be an IPAD-MD activity and is planned as a future expert group meeting (see 'Main Outcomes of the Stakeholder Meeting'). • Promote cross disciplinary understanding and opportunities for interaction (e.g. INFRAFRONTIER-Solve-RD / ERNs; IMPC/IRDIRC). • Prioritizing RD-relevant mouse models and identifying clinically relevant genes as priorities for functional studies (e.g. INFRAFRONTIER-Solve-RD / ERNs; IMPC/IRDIRC). • Proactive seeding of collaborations with clinical researchers and building on the example of the Rare Diseases Models and Mechanisms initiative. For example, active engagement of INFRAFRONTIER/IMPC in developing a brokerage system in EU with Solve-RD and ERNs. • Joint follow up grant application for seed funding of projects. • Possibly develop a priority list of rare diseases with IRDiRC to be de-risked through public efforts to enable therapeutic development. • Corporate and public co-operative efforts to bring rare disease drugs into the market. For example, involving EURORDIS which

	is active at the European Medicines Agency (as a member of relevant scientific committees) and in many key orphan medicines areas.
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Dr. Jan Hrušák, vice-chair of ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) presented on long-term sustainability of research infrastructures (RIs). He stressed that the recommendations published in ESFRI Scripta Vol. II¹ are the building blocks for a European action plan that is currently being implemented and concluded with the next steps towards realising long-term sustainability of RIs which included sharing of good national practices, improving stability and predictability of RI funding and exploring further adjustment of regulatory framework.

Session 4 showcased latest advances in the use of mouse models in promising gene therapy applications. The talks presented mouse models as prominent preclinical model systems to develop gene therapy approaches for rare diseases like Crigler-Najjar syndrome, achromatopsia, Friedreich ataxia-associated cardiomyopathy and mucopolysaccharidosis. The presentations also highlighted the key challenges in choosing the appropriate models and safety assessment of AAV (adeno-associated virus)- mediated gene supplementation. Overall, the results of these studies provided strong evidence for the clinical translation of these AAV-based gene therapy approaches for the treatment of rare diseases.

Session 5 focused on gene editing tools and techniques for rare and common diseases like hearing loss, hematopoietic abnormalities and mitochondrial disorders. Two studies focused on the genetic engineering of hematopoietic stem/progenitor cells (HSPC) to treat primary immunodeficiencies and Fanconi Anaemia. Gene editing delivery methods like cationic lipid-mediated Cas9 delivery and mitochondrially targeted zinc-finger nucleases were exemplary state-of-the-art examples of the current status of gene therapy research. Similar to the previous session, these presentations also introduced some precision mouse models like a model for human genetic deafness (called the Beethoven mouse model) and a mouse model with pathogenic mitochondrial DNA mutations.

The last session of invited speakers covered the technical optimisation of CRISPR/Cas9 technology, new gene editing programs and ethical initiatives. The technical optimisation of CRISPR/Cas9 involved using split-inteins whereby Cas9 can be split and fused to the corresponding split-inteins moiety. This bypassed the packaging limit of AAV vectors. The second talk on this topic presented data that stated that human Cas9-induced single-strand template repair requires the Fanconi anaemia pathway. This has significant implications on the application of gene editing treatments. The last two talks of the session introduced the NIH Somatic Cell Genome Editing Program (SCGE) and ARRIGE (Association for Responsible Research and Innovation in Genome Editing).

Similar to the first day, the second day of the meeting also ended with stakeholder presentations that were selected from submitted abstracts. These included the characterisation of a pig model of Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome, preclinical studies on a mouse model of Lafora disease and novel prevention strategy for lethal mitochondrial cardiomyopathy. Lastly, Prof. Dr. Martin Hrabě de Angelis gave the closing remarks, thanked the organisers and presented the main highlights of the Stakeholder Meeting.

Conference Outlook

¹ ESFRI Scripta Volume II: Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures Author, European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Long-Term Sustainability Working Group

The general consensus from the meeting discussions was that mouse models are indispensable for the treatment of rare diseases and advancing gene therapy approaches as they provide precise preclinical models for the development of new therapeutic avenues for rare and common genetic disorders.

The main outcomes of the third stakeholder meeting were:

- The presentation of outstanding state-of-the-art use cases of model organisms in rare disease research and gene therapy applications.
- The conception of a data integration workshop involving model organism resources and rare disease clinical data. This will be executed as Expert Group Data and Resources Meeting VI (Milestone 18 and Deliverable 7.6) in the IPAD-MD amendment.
- Setting up interactions between international and European rare disease networks and programs like RDMM, Solve-RD and EJP-RD, and INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC partners.
- Showcasing preclinical testing of gene therapy approaches to cure human diseases.
- Detailed insight into ESFRI's recommendations for long-term sustainability of research infrastructures and the subsequent European action plan.
- Announcement of the next Stakeholder Meeting titled 'INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019 Helsinki' focusing on genetic variation, big data and ageing. This will be executed as Stakeholder Meeting III (Milestone 16 and Deliverable 2.7) in the IPAD-MD amendment.
- Promoting active synergy between mouse geneticists and human geneticists by providing collaborative mechanisms advancing rare disease research with model organisms.

INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019: Genetic Variation, Big Data and Ageing

Details

Dates: 03 – 05.06.2019

Venue: HANASAARI (HANAHOLMEN) - Swedish-Finnish Cultural Centre, Helsinki, Finland

Registrations: 200

Website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-research-infrastructure/public-relations/infrafrontier-stakeholder-meetings-0>

About the conference

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Conference 2019: Genetic Variation, Big Data and Ageing (3rd – 5th June 2019) was attended by 200 participants from more than 22 countries across Europe, East-Asia, North America and Australia, and was jointly organized with the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) in Helsinki, Finland. Biocenter Oulu from University of Oulu was the co-organiser and national local host of the event.

Understanding the role of **human genetic variation and its functional analysis** is the next big step in genomic and precision medicine. The collection of such genomic data and its analysis falls into the category of **big data sciences** that has become commonplace in the present biomedical research landscape. In addition to this need, an increasing worldwide ageing population warrants the **better understanding of the ageing processes and diseases associated with ageing** to not only improve longevity but also to improve the quality of long life. These ideas were the basis for the **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019**.

This conference boosted the sustainability of INFRAFRONTIER by providing an excellent opportunity to better align INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms with current ageing and big

data initiatives. It also supported interactions with human genetics centres and clinical consortia to promote the functional analysis of human genetic variation.

The Stakeholder Meeting was broadly divided into the following sessions:

1. Genomic big data from population isolates
2. IMPC: Emerging insights into genomic and precision medicine
3. Understanding genetic variation using IMPC big data
4. Model organisms in ageing research
5. Animal models for studying genetic variation
6. Stakeholder presentations

The main objectives of the conference were:

- To raise awareness of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms among the population genetics and ageing research community.
- To develop collaborative opportunities in advancing functional genetic variation and ageing research with model organisms.
- To present use cases for the utility of model organisms to study genetic variation in population isolates and decipher ageing mechanisms.
- To strengthen interactions with ageing and population genetics research consortia.
- To showcase emerging insights from IMPC towards understanding functional genetic variation and developing precision medicine.

Agenda

The conference agenda can be found [here](#).

Conference Overview

Prof. Dr. Martin Hrabě de Angelis started off the conference with a welcome talk that included a brief introduction of INFRAFRONTIER, IMPC and the goals of the conference. Riina Vuorento from the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture welcomed all the participants and highlighted the importance of data generation, storage and access to and between distributed European infrastructures. Dr. Riitta Maijala (Vice President for Research, Academy of Finland) briefly introduced the Finnish Research Infrastructure (FIRI) funding scheme, its key principles of action and Finland's strategy and roadmap for RIs 2014 - 2020. Next was a snapshot of Biocenter Finland, nationwide research-infrastructure network, given by its Director Dr. Marja Makarow.

The first keynote lecture was given by Prof. Dr. Taina Pihlajaniemi, a pioneer at the forefront of extracellular matrix (ECM) and collagen research. Dr. Pihlajaniemi showcased the importance of mouse models in understanding the interplay between membrane-associated collagens with interrupted triple-helices (MACITs) and multiplex collagens in the ECM. She also described the mechanisms and their significance in development and tumorigenesis.

Session 1: Genomic Big Data from Population Isolates started with a keynote lecture by Prof. Dr. Aarno Palotie about the Finnish Disease Heritage and FinnGen, a large public-private

partnership aiming to collect and analyse genome and health data from 500,000 Finns by the year 2023. In the first year and a half, by utilising the samples collected by a nationwide network of biobanks, FinnGen has delivered genotype and health data from 142,000 Finns and started a collaborative project to study genetic impacts on health over time. This segued into another population genome project from the Faroe Islands called FarGen presented by Dr. Ellefsen. FarGen is coordinated by the Genetic Biobank of the Faroe Islands and at present 2000 individuals have signed up with 1532 blood samples collected. The data from these samples is used to perform linkage studies among families and search for large chromosomal regions that segregate to affected individuals more often than would be expected by chance - an effective approach for finding rare variants with large. Session 1 was concluded by Dr. Hardip Patel from the National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, Australia who presented strong arguments for the use of diversity inclusive reference data for human genomics research and clinical use, and the need for standards in human genomic analysis to achieve interoperable data.

Session 2 was assigned for the IMPC and was split into three parts. Session 2A started with an introductory talk by Prof. Dr. Steve Brown that summarised the status quo and future plans for the IMPC. Dr. Kalliopoi Kostelidou, the new Program Manager for the IMPC briefly introduced herself and IMPC's preparation for Horizon Europe. The rest of the session 2A and 2B showcased the progress, updates and impactful results from the various IMPC working groups that included age-related phenotyping, immunophenotyping, behaviour, cardiovascular and metabolism, embryo phenotyping and morphology.

The third keynote between sessions 3 and 4 was by Prof. Alitalo on translational insights to vascular growth factors. Prof. Alitalo presented examples of the translational therapeutic potential of vascular endothelial growth factors and angiopoietins. He also recapitulated the recent ground-breaking discovery of meningeal lymphatic vessels by his group, who attended the conference to facilitate further collaboration with INFRARONTIER. Prof. Alitalo ended his talk by underscoring the therapeutic potential of lymphangiogenic growth factors and their inhibitors in treating neurodegenerative and neuroinflammatory diseases.

Session 4 was focussed on model organisms in ageing research and comprised of diverse topics ranging from the development of growth factor therapies for Parkinson's (Dr. Saarma) to the use of home-cage monitoring to refine behavioural characterization of aging in mice (Dr. Ulfhake) and how ageing phenotypes unfold across the lifespan of mice and humans (Dr. Ehninger). The talks also showcased the use of state-of-the-art biomedical technologies like single cell sequencing to investigate if cell-to-cell gene expression variability increases during ageing on a genome-wide level (Dr. Martinez-Jimenez), and animal and patient-derived organoids for modelling premature ageing syndromes (Dr. Reversade). The Poster Session took place in the middle of session 4 with 23 posters selected from submitted abstracts.

The final day of the conference started with session 5 that focused on studying genetic variation using animal models. Research projects utilising mouse models to study the mechanisms for mitochondrial disorders (Dr. Suomalainen), complex multi-focal diseases (Dr. Iraqi) and unravelling the genetics behind complex neurological disorders in humans by using DNA samples from pet dogs (Dr. Lohi) were presented.

The last session of the conference consisted of five stakeholder presentations that were selected from submitted abstracts and showcased work involving advanced bioinformatics resources to improve drug development processes and success of clinical trials (Dr. Rhodes), patient-derived tumor xenograft (PDX) models as important preclinical models (Dr. Leucci), omics profiling to identify metabolic profiles of kidney progenitors (Dr. Kuure) and complementary Euro-Biolmaging services for INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC members (Dr. Kankaanpää).

Conference Outlook

The main outcomes of the conference were:

- Showcasing two population genetics projects, FarGen and FinnGen, to the mouse research community and highlighting the importance of biobanking in identifying novel human disease loci.
- Presenting IMPC's contribution to genomic medicine with scientifically relevant and diverse research contributions from the different working groups along with upcoming publication plans.
- Opportunities for discussing the future of IMPC and its focus on the study of functional genetic variation.
- Introducing INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms to the population genetics research community.
- Setting up the stage for potential collaborations that include:
 - INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC members and the above-mentioned genomics project. For example, mouse knockout phenotypes that contribute to identification of genes contributing to human traits that are examined by FinnGenn.
 - Integration of dog and mouse phenotypic data could lead to new insights into human disease mechanisms.
 - Euro-Biolmaging and IMPC to explore setting up collaborative analysis and setting up long-term sustainability of IMPC image data.

INFRAFRONTIER Cancer Conference 2020: Targeting Cancer with Animal Models

Details

Dates: 07 – 08.10.20

Venue: Online (GoToWebinar)

Registrations: 206

Website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-conference-2020>

About the conference

After cardiovascular diseases, cancer is the leading cause of death and one of the major contributors to premature deaths in the EU. In 2016, one quarter (26.0%, 13 million people) of the total number of deaths in Europe were due to cancer. The EC has taken a strong stand in the fight against cancer with the inception of its [Europe Beating Cancer Plan](#) and the [Cancer Mission area](#) for the Horizon Europe framework beginning in 2021. The Cancer Mission is guided by experts from various facets of cancer treatment like cancer research, innovation, policy, healthcare provision and practice. These experts constitute the Cancer Mission Board.

With recent biomedical advances it has become obvious that cancer is not a single disease but a collection of several diseases. What these maladies have in common is the uncontrolled growth of cells disrupting the delicate balance between life and death; proliferation and apoptosis. Cancer research and treatment are particularly challenging because tumours exhibit different tumour origins and mechanisms for subverting the natural cellular checkpoints for survival, death, immune evasion, drug sensitivity and metastatic invasion. To further complicate matters, this heterogeneity is also prevalent among cells of the same tumour. Thus, the treatment of cancers requires a more personalised approach customised towards a particular tumours genetic and cellular perturbations.

Mouse models are used in cancer research to explore the causality between cancer genes and carcinogenesis, and as models to develop and test novel therapies. Mouse models have become ideal models for precise individualized cancer therapy thanks to the advancements in CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing, patient xenograft implantation and microbiota studies enabling them to effectively replicate the aforementioned cancer heterogeneity in a laboratory setting.

The INFRAFRONTIER Conference 2020 'Targeting Cancer with Animal Models' aimed to showcase such innovative animal models used in cancer research and also introduce the Cancer Mission Board to the cancer research community.

The main objectives of this conference were to:

- Present latest research on innovative cancer models
- Showcase INFRAFRONTIER services for cancer research
- Align the scientific strategy on cancer mouse models with the Horizon Europe Cancer Mission

Agenda

The conference agenda can be found [here](#).

Conference Overview

Session 1 highlighted some of the latest innovative *in vivo* and *in vitro* cancer models and started with a Keynote from Dr. Hellmut Augustin. Dr. Augustin presented the need for better preclinical tumour models in the current cancer research landscape and reviewed the current state-of-the-art of contemporary preclinical tumour model research, discussed some major bottlenecks and proposed a platform of GEMM-derived syngraft models and novel focal surgical GEMM models (for metastasis research) that could contribute to overcoming some of the current limitations and bottlenecks.

Dr. Enzo Medico argued for the robustness of PDXs as preclinical models for predicting drug response. He presented his extensive analytical work that negated the possibility of a selection pressure imposed on a human tumour growing in a mouse microenvironment driving mouse-specific genetic evolution of PDXs, compromising their reliability as human cancer models.

Mathew Garnett updated the efforts of the Human Cancer Models Initiative (HCMI) to create a new biobank of molecularly-annotated tumour organoids as a community resource. He also presented use cases on how organoid cultures are used in chemical and genetic screens to identify new molecular targets and biomarkers of therapy response. These early studies laid the foundation for a next-generation tumour organoid functional genomics platform and help guide the development of future precision cancer medicines.

Dario Longo showcased some of the innovative MRI-based approaches developed in his group for imaging *in vivo* tumour acidosis. These techniques can be exploited for evaluating the relationship of tumour acidosis with cancer metabolism and metastatic potential as well as for assessing treatment response to novel anticancer therapies. According to Dr. Longo, tumour pH imaging is emerging as an innovative diagnostic tool for characterizing tumour metabolism and evaluating treatment responses.

Other talks in the session illuminated the role of cyclooxygenase 2 in driving inflammation in pancreatic cancer (Dr. Karin Müller-Decker), the use of genetically engineered mouse models and PDX models to genetically dissect breast cancer development, therapy response and resistance (Dr. Jos Jonkers) and the serendipitous discovery that glioblastoma cells were sensitive to lysosomal membrane permeabilization (Dr. Pirjo Laakkonen).

Session 2 consisted of presentations from INFRAFRONTIER partners and aimed to spotlight the different types of cancer research carried out in the INFRAFRONTIER consortium. The session began with a keynote from Dr. Bernard Malissen (Head of CIPHE) on the use of mouse models and advanced multiparametric flow, mass, and spectral cytometry in investigating cancer immunotherapies.

Dr. Fabio Mammano presented his group's work on unravelling the role of connexin hemichannels in cancer photodynamic therapy using intravital multiphoton microscopy and a syngeneic mouse model of melanoma.

Dr. Fuad Iraqi described the identification of modifier genes associated with cancer developments by quantitative trait loci (QTL) analysis on collaborative cross mice.

Dr. Birgit Rathkolb presented her clinical and histopathological characterisation of a rodent model of KIT-induced human cancer that is a novel ENU-induced mouse mutant carrying the homologous mutation to an Imatinib-resistant mutation found in different types of human cancer in the murine Kit protein.

Dr. Valerio Izzi showcased how his team used big data to identify ECM moieties associated with AML progression and chemoresistance and identified Collagen XVIII (Col18a1) as an important gene for AML disease progression.

Planned for session 1 but due to a scheduling conflict, Dr. Bodo Lange presented about the H2020 project CanPathPro in this session. The unique project deals with building and validating a computational predictive modelling platform applied to cancer. In essence it employs a highly integrative systems biology approach for generating and validating new hypotheses on cancer pathways signaling and cross-talk, identifying new signal flow and suggesting new ways to interfere with tumour growth.

Session 3 focussed on European cancer research policy and emphasized possible synergy between the European Cancer Mission and the European RIs namely INFRAFRONTIER, EurOPDX, Euro-Bioimaging, Instruct and EU-OPENSURE. The session consisted of presentations from the above RIs and the Cancer Mission (Dr. Tomi Mäkelä and Dr. Bettina

Ryll), and concluded with a panel discussion with the speakers. The session started with a poll asking the audience if they are familiar with the Cancer Mission and its objectives (shown below) and segued into Dr. Tomi Mäkelä's talk about the Cancer Mission and its recommendations.

How familiar are you with the Cancer Mission (Horizon Europe) and its objectives?

030

Dr. Mäkelä introduced the goals of the Horizon Europe Missions to give direction to European research and innovation in solving society's pressing challenges and to involve citizens and stakeholders more closely in setting research priorities. The Cancer Mission consists of 15 high-level independent experts from research, academia, medicine, patient organisations, international agencies etc. along with a nominated assembly of 26 experts from cancer organisations and stakeholders. The Cancer Mission brings forward a novel opportunity to boost EU efforts to conquer cancer and aims to save more 3 million lives as well as improve the lives of cancer survivors. The five main intervention areas to accomplish include – understanding, prevention, diagnosis and treatment, quality of life and equitable access. As a first step, the Cancer Mission Board recently finalised a proposal called 'Conquering Cancer: Mission Possible – Report of the Mission Board' that details 13 recommendations (shown below) for action.

13 Recommendations for bold actions

- 1 Launch UNCAN.eu – a European Initiative to Understand Cancer
- 2 Develop an EU-wide research programme to identify (poly-) genic risk scores
- 3 Support the development and implementation of effective cancer prevention strategies and policies within Member States and the EU
- 4 Optimise existing screening programmes and develop novel approaches for screening and early detection
- 5 Advance and implement personalised medicine approaches for all cancer patients in Europe
- 6 Develop an EU-wide research programme on early diagnostic and minimally invasive treatment technologies
- 7 Develop an EU-wide research programme and policy support to improve the quality of life of cancer patients and survivors, family members and carers, and all persons with an increased risk of cancer
- 8 Create a European Cancer Patient Digital Centre where cancer patients and survivors can deposit and share their data for personalised care
- 9 Achieve Cancer Health Equity in the EU across the continuum of the disease
- 10 Set up a network of Comprehensive Cancer Infrastructures within and across all EU Member States to increase quality of research and care
- 11 Childhood cancers and cancers in adolescents and young adults: cure more and cure better
- 12 Accelerate innovation and implementation of new technologies and create Oncology-focused Living Labs to conquer cancer
- 13 Transform cancer culture, communication and capacity building

Image from Cancer Mission [online slides](#)

Dr. Mäkelä briefly described some of the recommendations that were relevant to the conference and its attendees. These recommendations included identification of poly-genic risk scores (#2), optimisation and development of screening programmes (#4), development of early diagnostic and minimally invasive technologies (#6), setting up a network of comprehensive cancer infrastructures (#10) and acceleration of innovation and implementation of new technologies (#12). He also described recommendation 1 – UNCAN.eu in detail. This is essentially a new level of European-level investment in innovative research that focuses on how cancers initiate, develop and spread, promoting large-scale high-potential/high-risk projects, leveraging relevant EU RIs and investing in the development of new models and technologies. This initiative will include current RIs, large-scale projects, cancer research platforms, patient organisations (shown below) and will have data sharing and integration as a key component.

#1 UNCAN.eu – potential stakeholders

Dr. Mäkelä concluded with the next steps of the Cancer Mission in further fleshing out the recommendations and implementing them in Horizon Europe and answered some questions from the audience regarding including mouse models in recommendation 10 and the expected budget of the Cancer Mission.

Bettina Ryll

After losing her husband to Melanoma, Dr. Ryll founded a European patient network called the Melanoma Patient Network Europe (MPNE). With a medical degree and a PhD in Biomedical Sciences, her interest is in patient-centric research and today, the network is involved in numerous research initiatives. She also represents patient organisations in the European Cancer Mission Board. In her talk, BR reflected on the unique perspective on research that patients can provide- and how to leverage its benefits. Dr. Ryll explained that including patients in medical research, among other things, is beneficial and leads to responsibility and better accountability of researchers towards society and also helps to identify which elements of research projects are critical to patient care. Concerning mouse models, she emphasised that such models should clearly describe their ability to reflect or model the human cancerous phenotypes like tumour progression, metastasis etc. Additionally, she cautioned against over-selling scientific results as guaranteed cures as this can significantly harm the research field. Dr. Ryll closed her talk by giving some pointers on how to successfully involve patients in research that included identification of right patient candidates, anticipating a significant investment in time and money as this involves interfacing different fields and emphasising education and training on both sides.

Panel Discussion: How can European Life Science Research Infrastructures contribute to the Cancer Mission?

The panellists consisted of the speakers from session 3:

Michael Räß (Panel Chair)- INFRAFRONTIER, Germany

Tomi Mäkelä - Helsinki Institute of Life Science (HiLIFE), Finland; Member of EU Cancer Mission Board

Massimiliano Borsani - EurOPDX, Italy

John Eriksson - Euro-Biomedicine (EuBi), Finland

Susan Daenke - Instruct - ERIC, UK

Bahne Stechmann - EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC (EU-OS), Germany

Bettina Ryll - Melanoma Patient Network Europe (MPNE); Member of EU Cancer Mission Board

The panel discussion started with asking the audience's opinion if the European RIs from session 3 could contribute to the cancer mission.

Panel Discussion: Do you think the European RIs could contribute to the Cancer Mission?

0 2 1

Yes

No

0 %

Don't know

0 %

The unanimous answer was yes - the participants think that European RIs could play a major role in the Cancer Mission.

Question to all panellists: What roles can EU RIs play in the Cancer Mission?

Bettina Ryll stated that many people do not know about EU BMS-RIs. A significant effort in communication is needed to make patients, researchers and policy makers aware of the RIs and their resources and services. It is also very important to leverage and cleverly use their large catalogue of available resources and services along with the extensive expertise in the Cancer Mission. In essence, there is a need for more meetings and discussions, more exposure and better connection between the EU- RIs, Cancer Mission and patient organisations.

Bahne Stechmann stressed that the interdisciplinarity and collaboration, both within and between RIs, brings researchers from different expertise together under a common goal. For example, in EU-OPENSREEN cell biologists, assay developers, drug screening specialists, chemists, data specialists etc. work together to develop small molecule drugs for specific diseases. This feature of RIs can be a huge asset to collective endeavours like the Cancer Mission.

Susan Daenke explained that structural biology is fundamental research financed with public funds, marred high patient expectations and a slower research pace compared to translation research. However, it can be expedited as seen in the COVID-19 pandemic owing to good collaborative networks, access to open data, sharing of protocols, reagents, tools etc. RIs like Instruct can use their network ecosystem to meet such demands and expectations which would be useful for the Cancer Mission.

John Eriksson also underscored the importance of the interdisciplinary research done in RIs for the Cancer Mission and on working on the perception of the RIs by the public, funders, users, scientists, policy makers etc. In general, RIs are not very visible and not branded well enough. Their value proposal for the society is not very clear and substantial effort is required in this direction.

Massimiliano Borsani stated that RIs can be the foundations to address some of the Cancer Mission recommendations as RIs bring available publicly funded resources and services together. Most of these can be adapted to aid in the Cancer Mission and there is no need create them from scratch. This would save huge time, efforts and funds. In addition, most BMS-RIs have experience working together in joint-RI projects like CORBEL, EOSC-Life etc. and can easily do so again to support the Cancer Mission.

Michael Raess highlighted the role of RIs like INFRAFRONTIER in providing standardization and increasing the overall quality of preclinical research. RIs put a lot of effort in QM, QC, protocol development, distribution of standards. As a result, users follow these standards when they use these services and resources. This improves the quality of research outputs and avoids wastage of time and funding on research that cannot be reproduced or validated.

Tomi Mäkelä explained that the Cancer Mission has momentum and is a good device to make a change especially for institutes organised at the EU-level like the BMS-RIs. BMS-RIs can have a significant impact on the Cancer Mission as showcased in this session. However, a cooperative concerted effort is required to initiate actions at the EU-level using appropriate funding instruments.

Question from the audience: Can RIs contribute to UNCAN.eu (a European Initiative to Understand Cancer) as multi-RI consortia offering services across different scientific domains?

Tomi Mäkelä disclosed that past and current RI-consortia were used to develop the UNCAN.eu initiative. Indeed, multi-RI consortia and projects like CORBEL, EOSC-Life, LS RI etc. could form the cornerstone of a future UNCAN.eu platform. Such consortia would also allow BMS-RIs to be heard among the various Cancer Mission stakeholders.

Question from the audience: Would Patient Organisations be interested in being included in RI projects?

Bettina Ryll explained that it depends on the patient organisations (POs). It is important to remember that such initiatives are a type of citizen's movement and often reflect the interest of the founders. This needs to be considered before involving POs. In her experience, people are very interested in science and appreciate good communication efforts. For example, MPNE has found that a 45-minute informal chat session with scientists have proven to be very successful in their meetings. Another thing to keep in mind is to avoid adding POs as afterthoughts to Communication and Dissemination work packages in H2020 calls, especially after the budgets have been allocated.

Question to all panellists: To which Cancer Mission Recommendation (except 1 and 2) could your RI contribute the most?

John Eriksson: Apart from 1 and 2, recommendations relating to therapies and prevention and subsequent recommendations derived from them are most relevant to Euro-BioImaging (EuBi) with teams of researchers already involved in this effort. Recommendation 6 (early diagnostic and minimally invasive treatment technologies) is also where EuBi can contribute the most.

Massimiliano Borsani: Recommendation 5 pertaining to personalised medicine is where EurOPDX can contribute the most with cutting-edge preclinical facilities for testing personalised treatments on PDX cancer models. Recommendation 10 (Comprehensive Cancer Infrastructures) is also promising with EurOPDX's close scientific networks linking cancer clinics and labs.

Bettina Ryll: Recommendations 1 to 5 sit comfortably within the range of involvement for MPNE. Recommendation 12 dealing with accelerating innovation and implementation of new technologies is very relevant to POs in order to keep pace with emerging cutting-edge technologies, new therapeutics demands and emerging requirements in the research field. MPNE can also help with integration with other fields in cancer research. Recommendation 13 is about communication and is also very important as most research institutes suffer from poor communication to relevant shareholders.

Bahne Stechmann: Early recommendations fall into the ballpark for EU-OPENSREEN (EU-OS). Recommendation 5 for personalised medicine is especially relevant with a number of small molecule cancer drugs from EU-OS approved by the FDA and EMA. Moreover, RIs like EU-OS also play an important role in de-risking certain classes of drug targets like protein kinases. A large number of small molecule cancer drugs are now available against protein kinases with a concurrent rise in their interest thanks to academic contributions in improving their targetability. Thereby, paving the way for personalised medicine approaches.

Michael Raess: Recommendations 3 (cancer prevention strategies), recommendation 4 (screening and early detection), recommendation 5 (personalised medicine) and recommendation 13 (communication) could be where INFRAFRONTIER and its mouse clinics could contribute with specialised mouse models, phenotyping and early detection platforms, animal imaging facilities, biomedical screening services and cancer meetings.

Recommendation 10 (CCI) that deals with improving research quality and patient care could be interesting for INFRAFRONTIER.

Conference Outlook (Martin Hrabe de Angelis):

- 1) Animal models especially mouse models play an important role in basic and translational cancer research as well as in advancing strategies for prevention, diagnosis and therapy.
- 2) Cellular models and organoids are impressive *in vitro* models for cancer research. They cannot replace animal models as they lack complex organ crosstalk, immune system etc. but together with animal models efficiently complement existing biological tools to study cancer.
- 3) RIs are scientific platforms with high quality of research and reproducibility. They are also immense knowledgebases for the scientific community and provide access to information like experimental protocols, QC requirements etc.
- 4) It is high time to organise the RIs, researchers and patient communities in order to leverage complementary services and consolidate efforts.
- 5) The Cancer Mission is in a favourable position to unify these services with patient involvement, care and treatment towards a concerted effort to fight cancer.